

Terahertz-bandwidth photonic fractional Hilbert transformer based on a phase-shifted waveguide Bragg grating on silicon

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We propose and experimentally demonstrate the first THz-bandwidth on-chip photonic fractional Hilbert transformer. The reported design uses a novel approach, based on a uniform and non-apodized single-phase-shifted integrated waveguide Bragg grating on silicon, where the fractional order P can be engineered by simply varying the effective index modulation δn . Experimental results for $P = 1.5$ show very low processing error for broad range of pulse bandwidths between 77 GHz and 2.07 THz, corresponding to a time-bandwidth product (TBP) as high as 27.

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In applications such as radar, communication systems, image processing, computing and networking, an important signal processing operation is temporal Hilbert transformation (HT). A temporal HT is essentially an all-pass filter providing a discrete phase shift of π (integer HT) or a fraction of π (fractional HT) at the filter's central frequency. In recent years, photonic techniques have been proposed to implement this function, providing unprecedented speeds and bandwidths compared to electronic solutions, reaching the THz range [1–3]. Among these techniques, integrated photonic approaches are particularly attractive as they offer extreme compactness, simplicity and low sensitivity to environmental effects. In addition, when realized with CMOS compatible fabrication equipment, they have the potential for low unit cost, facilitating their use in practical applications [4]. The fastest photonic on-chip HT reported to date offered a bandwidth limited to approximately two hundred GHz [5]. Recently, Sima et al. [6] demonstrated the first THz-bandwidth 1st-order (integer) photonic Hilbert transformer fabricated in a silica-on-silicon platform. Two main issues, however, can be found in their approach, which is based on a waveguide Bragg grating (WBG) created in glass through a photosensitive process. The UV writing method is

limited in terms of the effective index modulation δn or the related coupling strength ($< 10^{-3}$) [6] which in turn requires gratings with long lengths (in the order of 1 cm) to achieve the desired performance. In addition, complicated apodization profiles are required, which are not trivial to realize using the UV writing method. In this work, we demonstrate the first integrated photonic fractional Hilbert transformer (FHT) fabricated through a standard CMOS photolithographic process, capable of efficiently processing optical pulses with THz bandwidths. The FHT is based on a very simple, uniform and non-apodized phase-shifted waveguide Bragg grating (PS-WBG), where the fractional order can be chosen by design, by simply engineering the effective index modulation δn . The resulting structure is also extremely compact compared to previous demonstrations, with a total grating length of only 65 μm .

The transfer function of a FHT is given by the expression

$$H_{\text{FHT}}(\omega) = \begin{cases} \exp(jP\frac{\pi}{2}) & \omega < 0 \\ 0 & \omega = 0 \\ \exp(-jP\frac{\pi}{2}) & \omega > 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where j is the imaginary unit, $\omega = \omega_{\text{opt}} - \omega_0$, ω_{opt} represents the optical frequency variable and ω_0 is the carrier frequency of the optical signal to be processed, and $P \in [0, 2]$ is the fractional order of the FHT [5, 7]. This ideal transfer function can be approximated by

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Fig. 1. Schematic layout of the PS-WBG

the response of a physical filter realized with a phase-shifted waveguide Bragg grating, operated in reflection, integrated in a silicon-on-insulator (SOI) technology [9]. This novel approach translates into an extremely simple layout, consisting of a uniform (i.e. non-apodized) WBG with a single phase shift (Fig. 1).

The effective index modulation is defined as the variation of the effective index of the corrugated waveguide forming the WBG across the length of the grating. Wide and narrow sections will have an effective index $(n + \delta n)$ and $(n - \delta n)$, respectively, where n is the effective index of the uncorrugated waveguide. The correspondance between the effective index modulation and the corrugation width of the waveguide shows a linear proportionality, and it has been extracted from experimental results on gratings with different corrugation widths previously fabricated with the same 193 nm lithographic process [8]. Fractional orders between 1 and 2 have been designed and simulated, and the case $P = 1.5$ has been experimentally realized and tested, as described in the following. As an example, Fig. 2 shows the simulated frequency responses obtained with three values of δn : 0.01, 0.04 and 0.06. Those index modulation values implement fractional orders of 1.05, 1.67 and 1.9, respectively, as can be seen from Fig. 2(b). This result proves the flexibility of this approach while retaining a very simple waveguide layout. It is also important to note that the passband width, the quality factor of the notch and the insertion loss in band degrade when the index modulation decreases, that is, with fractional orders approaching 1 (the integer Hilbert transformer), Fig. 2(a). To analyze the effect of the passband degradation, we define a figure of merit that accounts for the minimum and maximum bandwidth of operation, namely the time-to-bandwidth product (TBP), defined as the ratio of the maximum bandwidth (BW_{\max}) to the minimum bandwidth (BW_{\min}) calculated at the point in which the spectral magnitude decreases by 3 dB from the maximum [2]:

$$\text{TBP} = \frac{BW_{\max}}{BW_{\min}} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 3 shows the relation of the fractional order and the TBP with the index modulation. As said before,

Fig. 2. Simulated magnitude (a) and phase (b) frequency responses of the PS-WBG for three different values of the index modulation

Fig. 3. Relation of the fractional order (left axis) and time-bandwidth product (right axis) with the index modulation. The TBP y-axis is represented in logarithmic scale.

when reducing the fractional order towards 1, the TBP decreases with δn due to the simultaneous reduction in the quality factor of the central notch and of the maximum bandwidth. To achieve a high TBP when P approaches 1 (integer HT), a complex grating apodization is needed, similar to the profile reported in previous designs of integer photonic Hilbert transformers (PHTs) [1–3, 5, 6].

The specific device demonstrated here is designed in a 220 nm (thick) \times 500 nm (wide) silicon strip waveguide [9]. 100 nm sidewall corrugations are used for the grating, with a period of 325 nm (Fig. 1). The phase-shift is introduced in the middle of the grating structure, with 100 grating periods on either side of the phase-shift, for a total length of the PS-WBG of approximately 65 μm . Grating couplers and a Y-branch are included on the chip to access the reflection response of the grating, without the need of an external circulator (Fig. 4).

An optical vector analyzer from Luna Innovations (OVA5000) has been employed to characterize the optical transfer function in reflection of the realized PS-WBG. The measured magnitude and phase responses of the grating are shown in Fig. 5 in comparison with the transfer function of an ideal FHT. The realized filter approximates very well the ideal response, with an

Fig. 4. Picture of the realized chip. (a) Schematic of the layout; (b) Y-branch used to access the reflection port; (c) SEM image of the rib waveguide with sidewall corrugations. (Image (a) edited from [9]; images (b)-(c) from [11])

Fig. 5. Measured reflection spectral response of the fabricated PS-WBG compared to the ideal FHT response, in magnitude (a) and phase (b)

instantaneous bandwidth as wide as 16.8 nm (2.14 THz) and a phase transition of 1.5π radians (equivalent to a fractional order of 1.5) around the central frequency. The reflection response showed a total insertion loss of approx. 18 dB that has been removed from the figure for ease of comparison with the ideal response. The insertion loss is mainly attributed to the grating couplers and the on-chip Y-branch [9]. The grating couplers exhibit a nearly flat transmission over the complete reflection band of the PS-WBG (Fig. 6). It is important to notice that the resonance depth at the center of the reflection band reaches approx. 40 dB, which represents a 20 dB improvement compared to other integrated photonic Hilbert transformers demonstrated to date [5, 6]. Based on the spectral response measurement in Fig. 5, and according to Eq. (2), we estimate a $TBP \approx 27$. In the following we use time domain characterization to prove that this frequency-domain estimate of the TBP is accurate.

Fig. 6. Measured transmission spectral response of the cascade of two grating couplers used for fiber-to-chip coupling, normalized to a 0 dB maximum transmission. The grating couplers exhibit maximum transmission, with a ripple of less than 2 dB, over the whole passband of the waveguide Bragg grating (1526 nm to 1546 nm).

In order to characterize the time-domain response of the device to a transform-limited Gaussian-shaped probe pulse, the method known as Fourier-transform spectral interferometry (FTSI) has been employed. In this method, a well-characterized input pulse is used as the reference itself [10]. An optical parametric oscillator (OPO) generates a Gaussian-like optical pulse, which is then limited in bandwidth employing a variable passband optical filter. The pulse is centered at 195.203 THz (1535.8 nm), the same frequency of the DPS-WBG notch. The filtered pulse enters a fiber-based interferometer, built using two 10:90 couplers, as in Fig. 7. The device under test is placed in the lower interferometer arm. The upper arm (reference arm) includes a tunable optical delay line (TODL), employed to adjust the time interval between the pulses propagating in the two arms. This interval can be accurately measured by connecting the interferometer output to a 12 ps detector (PD, New Focus 1014) and a 28 GHz oscilloscope (OSC). An erbium-doped fiber amplifier (EDFA) is used to amplify the optical signal before photodetection. A variable optical attenuator (VOA) is also inserted in the reference arm to equalize the intensities of the two pulses. An optical spectrum analyzer (OSA) with a minimum resolution of 0.01 nm has been employed to measure the spectra of the input reference pulse, of the filtered pulse and their linear interference at the interferometer output. These three spectra are then used to numerically reconstruct the complete time waveform of the processed pulse, in magnitude and phase. Minimizing the length of the fiber pigtailed of all the employed components allows to limit dispersion effects to negligible levels. Experiments have been performed for pulses of various durations, between 1.5 ps (≈ 300 GHz bandwidth) and 15 ps (≈ 30 GHz bandwidth), and the measured time domain pulses have been compared with the ideal responses, i.e. the simulated responses obtained by numerically filtering the measured input pulse with the ideal response shown in Fig. 5. In all the tested cases, the measured time domain pulses agree well with the ideal ones. Two examples are presented in Fig. 8, for a pulse duration

Fig. 7. Schematic of the employed FTSI setup for time-domain characterization of the photonic FHT

of 4 ps (a) and 1.5 ps (b) at full-width half maximum (FWHM), showing a root-mean square error (RMSE) of 2.44 % and 0.49 %, respectively. The residual deviations observed are attributed to experimental inaccuracies of the FTSI method and to imperfections in the spectral response of the fabricated device, including amplitude ripples and deviations in the phase response (Fig. 5).

Fig. 8. Time-domain experimental testing results. The figure shows the measured input pulse (solid line), simulated output pulse obtained by filtering the measured input pulse with an ideal Hilbert transformer (dashed line), and actual output pulse measured using FTSI technique (circled line), for input pulses with FWHM durations of 4 ps (a) and 1.5 ps (b). The pulse intensities have been normalized to unity for ease of comparison. Cross-correlation coefficient versus the FWHM bandwidth of the input Gaussian pulse (c).

The study has been further extended by analyzing the device processing accuracy as a function of the FWHM bandwidth of the input pulse, represented by the cross-

correlation coefficient ρ_{xy} between the intensity of the time domain waveform $x(t)$ obtained when an ideal Gaussian pulse is processed by an ideal FHT, and of the waveform $y(t)$ obtained by processing the ideal Gaussian pulse with the measured FHT response in Fig. 5. The percentage cross-correlation coefficient $\rho_{xy,\%}$ provides a precise estimate of the similarity between the two time domain waveforms and is defined as

$$\rho_{xy,\%} = \frac{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |x(\tau)||y(\tau)|d\tau}{\sqrt{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |x(\tau)|^2d\tau \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |y(\tau)|^2d\tau}} \times 100. \quad (3)$$

Fig. 8(c) shows the percentage cross-correlation coefficient as a function of the FWHM input pulse bandwidth. The highest degree of similarity between the waveforms is obtained for a pulse bandwidth of approximately 859 GHz (corresponding to a FWHM time-width of about 0.5 ps), with a $\rho_{xy,\%}$ as high as 98.3%. It is important to observe that the cross-correlation coefficient keeps above 89% for a broad range of pulse bandwidths between 77 GHz and 2.07 THz. This represents a TBP of approximately 27, in agreement with the value estimated through the analysis of the measured optical spectral response in Fig. 5. The $\rho_{xy,\%}$ was calculated with an input pulse spectrum centered at the notch of the DPS-WBG reflection band (Fig. 5). Simulations show that a misalignment of ± 400 GHz would reduce the maximum $\rho_{xy,\%}$ less than 0.1%. The notch frequency can be tuned varying the chip temperature, with a rate of approximately 9.44 GHz/ $^{\circ}$ C [11]. The reported device opens the path to realization of a number of on-chip ultrafast optical signal processing functionalities of potential interest for pulse shaping, communications, radar signal processing, image processing etc.

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